

Applying time-resolved photoluminescence in scanning near-field optical microscopy to map charge-carrier dynamics in CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals

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ABSTRACT

Charge-carrier dynamics in perovskite materials are commonly investigated using techniques that either provide spatially averaged information or probe only a single point, often overlooking nanoscale heterogeneities that critically influence device performance. In this work, time-resolved photoluminescence mapping in aperture-type scanning near-field optical microscopy was used to directly visualize charge-carrier behavior in CsPbBr₃ nanocrystal films, achieving sub-diffraction spatial resolution of ~150 nm and temporal resolution of 100 ps. Through the combination of near-field optical excitation and simultaneous topographical characterization, structural features were found to influence local optical and electronic properties. Spatial variations in photoluminescence intensity, emission wavelength, and carrier lifetimes were observed across quasi-continuous films formed by nanocrystal aggregation. These heterogeneities, which are highly relevant to optoelectronic and photonic applications, were shown to significantly affect carrier recombination dynamics. Notably, regions exhibiting red-shifted emission were found to have longer photoluminescence lifetimes, indicating a strong correlation between spectral properties and recombination processes. This study demonstrates how near-field time-resolved photoluminescence can serve as a powerful tool to probe local charge-carrier dynamics in perovskite materials and offers new insights for their more reliable and efficient integration into next-generation optoelectronic technologies.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Lead halide perovskites (LHPs), particularly CsPbBr₃, have emerged as a remarkable and highly promising material in recent times,^{1–4} generating a significant interest for optoelectronic applications, e.g., photovoltaics,^{5–7} energy harvesting,^{8,9} and radiation detection.^{10–12} Notable features include high photoluminescence quantum yield, long non-radiative recombination lifetimes,^{13–15} and the potential for optical cooling through phonon-assisted processes,¹⁶ along with the availability of cost-effective synthesis methods.^{17–20} The unique characteristics of CsPbBr₃ have not only

led to the exploration of novel optoelectronic applications but also instigated curiosity about the origin of the above-mentioned unique or favorable physical properties.^{21–23} Since the performance and stability of optoelectronic devices are often governed by nanoscale variations in charge-carrier dynamics, understanding how these processes vary spatially is essential for optimizing material functionality. Therefore, providing deeper insight into the origins of these properties and unlocking their full application potential require advanced characterization techniques capable of resolving spatial and temporal variations at the nanoscale.

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Although far-field (FF) photoluminescence (PL) and time-resolved PL (TRPL) spectroscopies provide insights into charge-carrier dynamics,²⁴ recombination mechanisms,^{25,26} and photophysical processes,²⁷ their diffraction-limited spatial resolution prevents access to nanoscale heterogeneities. To overcome this limitation, complementary high-resolution techniques are available. Cathodoluminescence (CL), for example, has been used effectively to probe luminescence at the nanoscale, producing a spatial resolution of down to ~ 10 nm.²⁸ Furthermore, time-resolved CL (TRCL) allows picosecond-scale measurements of charge-carrier lifetimes, providing information on carrier recombination pathways with high spatial precision.²⁹ However, for LHPs, the high-energy electron beams used in CL often introduce irreversible damage not only through knock-on displacement of atoms but also via radiolysis processes due to an inherent ionic character and moderate stability of the LHP crystals.^{30–32} Alternatively, near-field (NF) optical methods, such as scanning near-field optical microscopy (SNOM), offer a non-destructive route for high-resolution optical characterization, with spatial resolution exceeding the FF diffraction limit.³³ Among the SNOM variants, scattering-type SNOM (s-SNOM) achieves superior spatial resolution and is widely used for imaging optical near fields,^{34,35} but it typically detects elastically scattered light and lacks the spectral separation and temporal resolution needed for direct PL or charge-carrier lifetime measurements. In contrast, aperture-type SNOM (a-SNOM) enables the mapping of both propagating and non-propagating optical fields at the nanoscale and facilitates NF phase imaging using entirely NF-based holographic reconstruction.³⁶ The integration of NF excitation with PL^{37–39} and TRPL^{40–42} in a-SNOM represents a significant advancement, improving the spatial resolution of PL spectroscopy.

Previous studies have demonstrated the utility of a-SNOM for nanoscale PL mapping in various systems, such as InGaN quantum wells,⁴³ organic–inorganic hybrid perovskites,⁴⁴ and CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals (NCs).⁴⁵ However, while FF TRPL has been extensively used to study LHPs, its implementation in a-SNOM for direct spatial mapping remains unexplored.

Here, PL and TRPL in a-SNOM are presented as tools to spatially resolve charge-carrier recombination dynamics in CsPbBr₃ NC films, offering a comprehensive framework by which structural and optical characteristics can be correlated with sub-diffraction resolution (~ 150 nm). Through this approach, topography, PL, and TRPL lifetime maps are simultaneously acquired, enabling direct pixel-by-pixel correlation of local structural features, such as surface height variations, with photophysical parameters including PL intensity, peak wavelength, linewidth, and carrier lifetime. Compared to conventional FF methods, NF excitation is used to minimize the influence of optical diffraction and to improve localization of the excitation volume, thereby enhancing sensitivity to nanoscale heterogeneities in recombination dynamics. Using NF-excited TRPL measurements, it is revealed that regions of increased roughness, typically associated with NC aggregation, exhibit prolonged PL lifetimes and redshifted emission, suggesting links to weak quantum confinement effects⁴⁶ and photon recycling.⁴⁷ This correlative, high-resolution mapping approach is shown to provide a powerful method for studying spatially varying optoelectronic properties in perovskite materials, offering critical insights into structure–function relationships relevant for device optimization.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Sample preparation and dual-path a-SNOM instrumentation

In this study, colloidal CsPbBr₃ NCs synthesized by the hot-injection method, as previously reported in the literature,⁴⁸ were investigated. These NCs were subsequently drop-cast onto a 0.3 μm -thick fused silica substrate. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging revealed that significant clustering was exhibited by the NC films across the surface, with clusters typically around 1 μm small [Fig. 1(a)]. A more detailed view confirmed that individual NCs were well dispersed within these clusters [Fig. 1(b)]. The size distribution analysis, obtained from detailed SEM images and fitted with a Gaussian profile, indicated that the average NC diameter was (15.8 ± 1.4) nm [Fig. 1(c)].

To optically characterize these NCs with nanoscale spatial resolution, an a-SNOM integrated into a modified atomic force microscopy (AFM) module (LiteScope), operating in illumination mode, was implemented. The excitation source, a pulsed laser diode (PLD), was coupled into a single-mode optical fiber (SMF) with a metal-coated tapered tip, forming the a-SNOM probe [Fig. 1(d)]. This configuration enabled localized optical excitation of the sample at each scan pixel through a subwavelength tip aperture with 150 nm diameter. The probe was affixed to a tuning fork (TF) for shear-force feedback regulation, maintaining a constant tip–sample distance during scanning. For mechanical stability, adhesive was used to mount the probe onto the TF (Fig. S1 in the supplementary material). The a-SNOM probe was mounted on a three-axis probe holder equipped with motorized macro-positioning stages, allowing for coarse alignment with the collection optics. Fine scanning was achieved by attaching the sample to a three-axis piezoelectric stage (PS), which enabled sub-nanometer positioning precision during raster scanning beneath the stationary a-SNOM tip [Fig. 1(e)].

During operation, the sample was illuminated from the tip side in NF, and the resulting PL was collected in the FF transmission mode through the transparent substrate. The collected signal passed through a longpass filter (LF) to remove residual excitation light, was refocused using a tube lens (TL), and split into two parallel detection paths. One path was directed to an avalanche photodiode (APD) connected to a time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) module for TRPL measurements; the other path led to an imaging spectrograph (SP) coupled with a CCD camera for spectral acquisition. Signal splitting was achieved using a 1×2 single-mode fused fiber optic coupler with a 75:25 ratio, sending 75% of the light to the APD and 25% to the SP.

The schematic inset in Fig. 1(e) illustrates the NF excitation mechanism. While the excitation volume is predominantly confined by the 150 nm probe aperture, charge carriers in layered 2D perovskites can exhibit diffusion lengths exceeding 1 μm .⁴⁹ In contrast, in CsPbBr₃ NC films, diffusion is strongly limited, with reported lengths of 50–70 nm⁵⁰ and up to 200 nm under optimized conditions.⁵¹ As a result, radiative recombination may occur well beyond the initial excitation site. To ensure efficient collection of these spatially extended emission events, a 50 \times objective with a numerical aperture (NA) of 0.55 was employed. This configuration minimizes signal loss from lateral carrier diffusion by providing a

FIG. 1. (a) SEM image of the CsPbBr₃ NC film exhibiting significant clustering across the surface. (b) Detailed SEM view of CsPbBr₃ NCs drop-cast onto a fused silica substrate. (c) Size distribution histogram of the deposited NCs. (d) SEM image of an a-SNOM probe, highlighting the 150 nm aperture diameter in the inset. (e) Schematic of the experimental setup, including pulse laser diode (PLD), focus lens (FL), single-mode optical fiber (SMF), piezo stage (PS), tuning fork (TF) with an a-SNOM probe, 50× magnifying objective (MO) with 0.55 NA, longpass filter (LF), tube lens (TL), avalanche photodiode (APD), and spectrograph (SP). The inset illustrates the NF excitation of PL in a perovskite sample by an a-SNOM probe, indicating the diffusion length of radiative charge-carrier recombination and FF transmission/collection.

broader collection area. As demonstrated in previous studies,^{43,52,53} it enables direct observation of charge-carrier dynamics at the nanometer scale.

A major technical challenge in implementing PL and TRPL using a-SNOM is the inherently low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), caused by the limited optical throughput of subwavelength apertures. This limitation is further exacerbated at moderate excitation powers; in our setup, for instance, we used an average excitation power of 1 mW. To address this, a relatively large a-SNOM tip aperture diameter of 150 nm, greater than typically employed in high-resolution a-SNOM, was used to increase transmission while retaining sub-diffraction-limited excitation. Additionally, a dual-path detection approach enables the simultaneous acquisition of steady-state and TRPL signals. Through these enhancements, the applicability of a-SNOM to both PL and TRPL measurements was significantly improved. In particular, the capability for TRPL studies of perovskite NC films was established, addressing a previously unresolved limitation due to insufficient signal levels.

B. Topography validation: AFM vs a-SNOM mapping

AFM topography [Fig. 2(a)] revealed prominent height variations across the CsPbBr₃ NC film, with peak heights reaching up to 230 nm. Considering the average NC diameter of approximately 16 nm obtained from SEM [Fig. 1(c)], these height variations correspond to local aggregates composed of up to about 15 stacked NC layers, whereas thinner regions represent areas of only a few stacked NCs. The entire substrate is, however, uniformly covered by

the NC film, forming a quasi-continuous layer with locally varying thickness. The corresponding a-SNOM topography [Fig. 2(b)], acquired over the same region using shear-force feedback, preserved the general morphological features but exhibited a noticeably smoother and flattened appearance. This is particularly evident in the comparative line profiles [Fig. 2(c)], where the local height maxima measured by a-SNOM are systematically attenuated by approximately 20–30 nm, and feature widths are broadened relative to AFM. These differences stem from distinct tip-sample interaction regimes, as well as from the use of different probes in each technique, particularly their tip geometry and operational distance, which influence the spatial resolution and accuracy of topographic measurements. While AFM was performed in contact mode, providing direct surface contact and high vertical resolution, a-SNOM employs shear-force feedback that maintains an ~0–20 nm tip-sample gap.³³ Despite the resolution limitations, a-SNOM enables the simultaneous acquisition of the topography and optical response of the sample, providing a direct correlation between morphological and optical properties without the need for additional imaging techniques.

C. Sub-diffraction photoluminescence mapping: Near- vs far-field

To demonstrate the capability of a-SNOM for optoelectronic characterization, PL spectra obtained from NF and FF excitation were compared [Figs. 3(a) and 3(e)]. Representative spectra extracted from spatially resolved maps at selected positions (color-

FIG. 2. (a) AFM topography of the CsPbBr₃ NC film, revealing nanoscale surface features with height variations up to 230 nm. (b) Corresponding topographic map acquired by the a-SNOM probe using shear-force feedback. The a-SNOM topography qualitatively reproduces key structural features observed in AFM but exhibits slightly blurred contours due to the rather wide a-SNOM tip. (c) Comparative height profiles along the fast scan axis extracted from the AFM (black) and a-SNOM (red) topography maps, averaged over five adjacent pixels. The a-SNOM profile shows attenuated height maxima (by 20–30 nm) and broadened features.

coded) show clear PL emission in both configurations. Spectra taken in all points of the maps were fitted using a Gaussian function, with the extracted parameters subsequently used to generate spatial maps of peak intensity, full width at half maximum (FWHM), and peak wavelength.

The NF-excited PL maps [Figs. 3(b)–3(d)] reveal sub-diffraction spatial variations in emission characteristics. Notably, regions with increased PL intensity [Fig. 3(b)] also exhibit red-shifted PL [Fig. 3(d)]. FWHM values [Fig. 3(c)] range from 33 to 36 nm and show slight narrowing in areas of higher PL intensity. While similar inverse trends between FWHM and intensity have been previously linked to improved crystallinity and reduced

energetic disorder,⁴⁴ we refrain from overinterpreting this trend, as it may also arise from additional factors such as reabsorption effects, variations in local morphology, or measurement limitations.

To assess whether these spatial variations are specific to NF excitation, the same region was re-measured under FF conditions [Figs. 3(f)–3(h)]. Similar spatial trends are observed in PL peak intensity and wavelength. However, FWHM values in FF measurements [Fig. 3(g)] are significantly narrower, ranging from 14.5 to 16.8 nm. This discrepancy arises primarily from differences in spectral resolution and SNR between the two configurations. In NF-excited PL, limited light throughput through the subwavelength a-SNOM tip aperture results in reduced PL signal. A control experiment (Fig. S2 in the [supplementary material](#)) confirmed local signal enhancement, showing an $\sim 1.5\times$ increase in PL intensity when the tip was approached to the surface (NF condition) vs retracted by $1\ \mu\text{m}$ (FF condition). Nonetheless, the lower SNR in NF excitation (~ 10) compared to FF (~ 400) required a wider spectrograph entrance slit to increase collection efficiency, which in turn degraded spectral resolution (see Fig. S3 in the [supplementary material](#)). Additionally, different spectrometers were employed in NF and FF configurations, further contributing to the observed FWHM differences. Therefore, while NF data allow for the extraction of key emission characteristics with nanoscale spatial resolution, linewidth values should be interpreted with caution, particularly in direct comparison with FF data.

More broadly, direct comparisons between NF and FF PL measurements remain limited in the literature, especially for spatially resolved emission characteristics such as peak position, intensity, and linewidth. These comparative insights are crucial given the strong spatial heterogeneity in carrier recombination dynamics observed in perovskite NC films. The NF configuration employed here enables localized excitation through a subwavelength aperture, revealing spatial features with sub-diffraction resolution. Building on these findings, Sec. II D extends this comparative approach to TRPL mapping, a domain in which NF-FF comparisons are virtually absent, despite their potential to uncover nanoscale variations in carrier dynamics.

D. Nanoscale TRPL lifetime mapping

In Fig. 4(a), a PL lifetime map acquired under NF excitation is shown, in which nanoscale heterogeneity in carrier recombination dynamics can be observed. Decay curves extracted from representative positions [Fig. 4(b)] exhibit a wide range of lifetimes (1–5 ns). A corresponding lifetime map obtained under FF excitation [Fig. 4(c)] reveals comparable lifetime values and global spatial trends; however, differences in feature sharpness and spatial localization are evident.

These disparities are attributed to differences in excitation wavelength, optical detection configuration, and signal integration volumes, as detailed in the Methods section. A consistent increase in measured lifetimes by approximately 1 ns in low-lifetime regions is observed under NF excitation, as demonstrated in the red decay traces of Figs. 4(b) and 4(d). Notably, this discrepancy occurs in areas corresponding to sparsely distributed, non-aggregated CsPbBr₃ NCs. One possible explanation is that NF excitation, while not dramatically more confined than FF in this setup, still provides slightly improved spatial selectivity. This moderate localization may

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FIG. 3. Representative PL spectra (points) from (a) NF- and (e) FF-excited PL maps at positions marked with corresponding colors, fitted using a Gaussian function (solid line). NF spectra were acquired by a-SNOM (407 nm excitation) and FF spectra by confocal microscopy (355 nm excitation; see Methods). NF-excited PL maps of (b) peak intensity, (c) FWHM, and (d) peak wavelength. FF-excited PL maps of (f) peak intensity, (g) FWHM, and (h) peak wavelength.

enhance sensitivity to nanoscale variations in surface passivation. Regions with improved ligand coverage and fewer surface traps would exhibit longer PL lifetimes, which become more pronounced in the spatially resolved NF measurement.

The NF and FF measurements employed different excitation wavelengths and powers due to the instrument configuration: 407 nm ($0.2 \mu\text{W}$) for NF and 440 nm ($33 \mu\text{W}$) for FF. Both excitation levels correspond to single-exciton conditions (see Methods for detailed estimation). Previous work by Qin *et al.*⁵⁴ showed that in CsPbBr₃ NCs the single-exciton lifetime varies by less than 10% across excitation wavelengths between 325 and 440 nm, indicating that the small wavelength difference used here does not significantly affect the measured lifetimes. To further confirm that the applied excitation did not induce any local photobleaching or degradation, two consecutive NF scans of the same region produced nearly identical topography, PL intensity, and PL lifetime maps (Fig. S4 in the [supplementary material](#)). Moreover, continuous PL spectra recorded during tip approach and repeated steady-state PL spectra measured at the same sample position showed no reduction

in intensity or spectral shift. The observed variations between NF and FF maps, therefore, primarily reflect spatial heterogeneity and collection geometry rather than excitation bias. Although charge carriers can diffuse several micrometers before recombination, the ~ 150 nm NF excitation defines the dominant spatial sensitivity. The detected TRPL signal, thus, mainly reflects the dynamics of locally excited carriers, with minor contributions from short-range diffusion (see Methods for detailed discussion).

To verify that the NF signal genuinely reflects the photophysical response of the sample, the raw PL intensity recorded by the avalanche photodiode during the same a-SNOM scan is presented in Fig. S5 in the [supplementary material](#). This map was directly extracted from the photon counts detected in the TCSPC process and represents the integrated PL intensity. The resulting intensity map closely matches that shown in Fig. 3(b), confirming that the NF signal originates from actual PL emission and is not dominated by tip-related artifacts.

Although the a-SNOM tip could, in principle, act as a local optical antenna, similar to effects reported in tip-enhanced

FIG. 4. (a) PL lifetime map acquired under NF excitation, revealing spatial heterogeneity in carrier recombination dynamics. (b) TRPL decay curves extracted from selected positions (colored marked in a), fitted using a single-exponential decay model (solid lines). (c) Corresponding PL lifetime map obtained by FF excitation over the same region. (d) TRPL decay curves at selected positions (colored marked in c) under FF excitation.

photoluminescence (TEPL) and tip-enhanced Raman scattering (TERS),⁵⁵ no such influence was detected in this study. Control experiments presented in Fig. S6 in the [supplementary material](#) demonstrate that the fitted PL lifetimes for the approached and retracted positions are below 2%. This confirms that any tip-induced modification of the lifetime lies below our experimental sensitivity. Small residual fluctuations in the tip-sample distance (a few nanometers) may occur over uneven topography; however, such variations only modulate signal intensity and have a negligible effect on the extracted lifetimes, which depend on the temporal decay shape. These findings support the interpretation that the lifetime contrasts observed in NF maps are governed by intrinsic nanoscale variations in the sample, rather than experimental artifacts. Goodness-of-fit analysis of representative single-exponential decays is presented in Fig. S7 in the [supplementary material](#).

E. Pixel-by-pixel correlation of structural and optical parameters

A significant strength of the a-SNOM-based approach lies in its ability to simultaneously map topography, NF-excited steady-state PL, and TRPL with high spatial precision. This integration allows for direct, pixel-by-pixel correlation of structural and optoelectronic properties within a single scan, without the need for separate instruments, complex spatial alignment, or post-processing. To explore these correlations, scatterplots of topographic height vs PL peak intensity, spectral position, and carrier recombination lifetime were analyzed [Figs. 5(a)–5(d)].

Figure 5(a) reveals a notable non-monotonic relationship between PL peak intensity and topographic height. PL intensity initially increases with height, reaching a maximum around ~ 130 nm, after which it begins to decline. This turning point suggests the involvement of parasitic optical effects in thicker NC aggregates. For instance, photon reabsorption within dense films may reduce

outcoupling efficiency, resulting in lower PL intensity despite increased material volume. These observations emphasize that increasing NC film thickness or aggregation does not linearly enhance optical emission and must be carefully optimized to balance generation and emission.

In Fig. 5(b), TRPL lifetimes exhibit a generally increasing trend with height, particularly beyond ~ 100 nm, which may reflect altered recombination dynamics in aggregated regions. A similar trend is observed in Fig. 5(c), where elevated PL intensity correlates with extended lifetimes, albeit with significant scatter. While these results suggest that NC aggregation can influence radiative recombination behavior, the correlation is not universal, indicating that factors such as local defects, surface traps, or interparticle electronic coupling likely modulate the carrier lifetime.

A more consistent correlation emerges in Fig. 5(d), where redshifted PL peak emission, particularly in high-topography regions, aligns with longer PL lifetimes. Several factors may contribute to this behavior: (i) Weak quantum confinement effects: Larger NCs or aggregated structures experience reduced confinement, resulting in bandgap narrowing, redshifted emission, and extended carrier lifetimes. Wang *et al.*⁴⁶ demonstrated how weak quantum confinement in CsPbBr₃ NCs influences their photophysical properties, including PL lifetimes. (ii) Reabsorption and photon recycling: In aggregated NC regions, emitted photons can be reabsorbed and re-emitted, effectively extending the PL lifetime. This process, known in hybrid perovskite single crystals,⁵⁶ alters emission spectra and recombination dynamics. Similar effects in CsPbI₃ NCs⁴⁷ suggest that reabsorption in CsPbBr₃ aggregates enhances photon recycling, delaying carrier recombination. Although these two effects have distinct physical origins, one electronic and one optical, their coexistence provides a consistent explanation for the observed correlation between redshifted emission and prolonged lifetimes in thicker or aggregated regions. Additional correlation plots not shown in the main text are provided in Fig. S8 in the [supplementary material](#).

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FIG. 5. Pixel-wise correlation of structural and optical properties extracted from a single a-SNOM scan of a CsPbBr₃ NC film. (a) PL peak intensity as a function of topographic height. (b)–(d) Correlation of NF-excited TRPL lifetime with (b) height, (c) PL peak intensity, and (d) PL peak emission wavelength. Each point corresponds to a single pixel. Red points highlight regions with topographic height exceeding 100 nm.

These findings underscore the advantages of integrating TRPL with a-SNOM, enabling pixel-by-pixel correlation of topographic and optoelectronic properties, including PL intensity, spectral shifts, and carrier lifetimes, within a single measurement. This direct mapping approach eliminates the need for separate techniques, complex spatial alignment, and post-processing, significantly streamlining the analysis of charge-carrier recombination and material uniformity. While NF-excited PL provides unparalleled insights into localized optoelectronic behavior, its spatial resolution is inherently limited by the a-SNOM aperture size (~150 nm) and tip geometry. The trade-off between signal intensity and spatial resolution, dictated by aperture constraints, presents a challenge in achieving higher-resolution imaging. Despite these limitations, NF-excited TRPL establishes itself as a crucial tool for probing charge-carrier dynamics at the nanoscale, offering deeper insight into material heterogeneity.

III. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the unique capability of NF-excited TRPL in a-SNOM as a highly effective method for probing nanoscale charge-carrier recombination dynamics in CsPbBr₃ NC films. By integrating spatially resolved topography, steady-state PL, and TRPL measurements within a single, alignment-free platform, this approach provides a direct and high-resolution correlation between structural and optoelectronic properties. The results reveal that local morphological heterogeneities, specifically NC aggregation, lead to distinct signatures in both spectral and temporal PL behavior, characterized by redshifted emission and extended carrier lifetimes, implicating reduced quantum confinement and photon recycling as dominant mechanisms in these regions.

Beyond merely characterizing spatial inhomogeneities, this study positions TRPL in a-SNOM as a transformative tool for

investigating recombination pathways with sub-wavelength precision, offering new possibilities for uncovering structure–function relationships in complex perovskite systems. This methodology holds significant promise not only for fundamental studies of carrier dynamics but also for guiding the nanoscale optimization of emerging optoelectronic devices based on halide perovskites and related materials.

IV. METHODS

The morphology of CsPbBr₃ NCs was characterized using SEM and AFM. SEM images were acquired using a high-resolution FEI Helios microscope operated at 5 kV and 50 pA in immersion mode. AFM measurements were carried out using a Bruker Dimension Icon system with ScanAsyst-Air probes (triangular geometry, nominal tip radius: 12 nm).

Commercially purchased a-SNOM probes (NT MDT) with a nominal aperture diameter of 100 nm were post-processed in a TESCAN LYRA3 Focused Ion Beam-Scanning Electron Microscope (FIB-SEM). Using a Ga ion beam, the aperture was milled to a final diameter of 150 nm, balancing signal throughput against spatial resolution.

The topographic accuracy in the a-SNOM measurements was assessed by extracting cross-sectional line profiles along the fast scan axis from both AFM and a-SNOM maps [Fig. 2(c)], averaged over five adjacent pixels, to evaluate lateral broadening and height attenuation.

NF-excited PL and TRPL measurements were performed using an a-SNOM system coupled to a 407 nm pulsed diode laser (pulse width: 100 ps, repetition rate: 40 MHz, average power: 1 mW before fiber coupling). The average NF excitation power at the tip aperture was measured by approaching the a-SNOM probe to a calibrated photodiode power sensor (S120VC, Thorlabs), yielding $P = 0.2 \mu\text{W}$ at the sample. With a repetition rate of $f = 40 \text{ MHz}$, this corresponds to a per-pulse energy of $E_p = P/f = 5.0 \times 10^{-15} \text{ J}$. For an aperture diameter of 150 nm (illuminated area $A \approx 1.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^2$), the incident fluence per pulse is $F = E_p/A = 28 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$. Assuming a pulse duration of $\tau_p = 100 \text{ ps}$, the instantaneous intensity is $I = E_p/(A\tau_p) \approx 3 \times 10^5 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. At 407 nm (photon energy $h\nu = 4.88 \times 10^{-19} \text{ J}$), the corresponding photon fluence is $\Phi = (E_p/h\nu)/A \approx 6 \times 10^{13} \text{ photons cm}^{-2}$. Using a literature absorption cross section for CsPbBr₃ NCs ($\sigma \approx 1 \times 10^{-15} \text{ cm}^2$ at 400 nm),⁵⁷ the mean exciton occupancy per NC per pulse is $\mu = \Phi\sigma \approx 0.06$, confirming operation in the single-exciton regime. Two consecutive NF scans under these conditions produced identical PL intensity and PL lifetime maps (Fig. S4 in the supplementary material), demonstrating the absence of light-induced degradation or heating during measurement.

The a-SNOM was operated in shear-force feedback mode with a nominal aperture diameter of 150 nm, maintaining a tip–sample separation of 0–20 nm. PL maps were acquired by raster scanning with a pixel spacing of 100 nm. Spectra were collected using a Shamrock 303i spectrograph coupled to an iDus 420 CCD camera. To improve NF signal collection, the spectrograph slit width was increased, resulting in a moderate reduction of spectral resolution compared to FF measurements (see Fig. S3 in the supplementary material). According to the manufacturer's specification, the theoretical spectral resolution

of the Shamrock 303i spectrograph equipped with a 150 lines/mm, 500 nm blaze grating is 0.88 nm under narrow-slit conditions ($\sim 10\text{--}20 \mu\text{m}$). However, to compensate for the reduced photon throughput through the 150 nm a-SNOM aperture, the entrance slit was widened up to 2000 μm in the NF configuration. The dependence of the measured PL linewidth on slit width was experimentally verified (Fig. S3 in the supplementary material), showing that the FWHM decreases from ≈ 35 to 36 nm at 2000–2500 μm slits to ≈ 20 nm for slit widths of 30–50 μm . These results confirm that the intrinsic PL linewidth of the CsPbBr₃ film is already broad, with the instrumental contribution remaining comparatively small. In contrast, the FF configuration employed a single-mode fiber (effective entrance slit $\approx 5 \mu\text{m}$) and a spectrograph with 0.02 nm resolution, yielding measured PL linewidths of 14.5–16.8 nm.

The effective spatial resolution of the TRPL maps is determined by the combined effects of the NF excitation profile, carrier diffusion, and the optical collection geometry. The initial excitation is confined by the $\sim 150 \text{ nm}$ aperture of the a-SNOM probe, which defines the lateral extent of carrier generation. After excitation, charge carriers can diffuse laterally before radiative recombination, slightly extending the region from which PL is emitted. The carrier diffusion length in closely packed CsPbBr₃ NC films is typically 50–70 nm⁵⁰ and can reach up to $\sim 200 \text{ nm}$.⁵¹ These values are substantially shorter than the collection diameter ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$), determined by the collection optics (50 \times and 0.55 NA objective), and comparable to the NF excitation confinement (150 nm). Consequently, the effective spatial resolution is dominated by the $\sim 150 \text{ nm}$ excitation confinement, with carrier diffusion ($\sim 200 \text{ nm}$) contributing only minor additional broadening.

Pixel-wise Gaussian fitting was applied to the background-subtracted PL spectra to extract key parameters,

$$I(\lambda) = I_0 \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\lambda_{\text{fwhm}}}\right)^2\right], \quad (1)$$

where I_0 denotes the peak PL intensity, λ_0 denotes the peak emission wavelength, and λ_{fwhm} denotes the FWHM. A control experiment (Fig. S2 in the supplementary material) confirmed NF enhancement, showing an $\sim 1.5\times$ increase in PL intensity when the tip was in contact compared to a retracted position (1 μm above the surface).

FF-excited PL maps were acquired from the same regions using a WITec alpha300 R confocal microscope (40 \times objective, NA = 0.6) with a 355 nm continuous-wave laser (average power: 20 μW) in reflection mode. Spectra were collected using a WITec UHTS spectrometer with a back-illuminated EMCCD camera.

FF-excited TRPL measurements were conducted using fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM; Leica Stellaris 8 Falcon, 63 \times oil-immersion objective, NA = 1.4). Excitation was provided by a 440 nm pulsed white light laser (WLL) operating at a 40 MHz repetition rate, with an average power of 33 μW .

TRPL decays were fitted using a single-exponential model to extract carrier lifetimes,

$$I(t) = I_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right), \quad (2)$$

where I_0 is the initial PL intensity and τ is the PL lifetime.

Although carrier recombination in perovskite NC films can involve multiple channels leading to multi- or stretched-exponential behavior, the single-exponential model was adopted here to provide a consistent and quantitative comparison across the PL lifetime maps. To confirm that this simplified model sufficiently describes the measured kinetics, residuals of representative fits are shown in Fig. S7 in the [supplementary material](#).

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See the [supplementary material](#) for SEM images of the a-SNOM probe, PL spectra of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals measured at approached and retracted probe positions, the dependence of PL spectral width and amplitude on spectrometer entrance slit width, consecutive NF scans confirming measurement stability, NF PL intensity maps recorded simultaneously with TRPL data, additional TRPL measurements verifying NF enhancement, residuals of single-exponential decay fits, and extended correlation analysis of topography, PL, and lifetime maps.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

P. Klok: Conceptualization (lead); Investigation (lead); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (lead). **P. Liška:** Formal analysis (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **V. Krápek:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **O. Černek:** Software (equal). **Z. Nováček:** Methodology (equal); Software (equal). **T. Šamořil:** Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **P. Bouchal:** Conceptualization (equal); Visualization (equal). **M. Kratochvíl:** Methodology (equal). **F. Ulč:** Software (equal). **J. Čecháček:** Software (equal). **J. Spousta:** Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **T. Šíkola:** Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **P. Viewegh:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Resources

(equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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